

NOVO TESTE

```

11 "https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCpRZ4JVRJFdvCmQ06i
12 "https://www.linkedin.com/company/34891093/admin/"],
13 "potentialAction": {
14 "@type": "SearchAction",
15 "target": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/pages/search_resu
16 "query-input": "required name=search_term"
17 }},
18 {
19 "@context": "https://schema.org/",
20 "@type": "VideoObject",
21 "name": "5 elementos chave na construção de um site",
22 "@id": "https://youtu.be/mLpWVAoKB3A",
23 "datePublished": "2020-01-17",
24 "description": "5 elementos chave na construção de um s
25 "thumbnailURL": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-con
26 "thumbnail": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-conte
27 "duration": "T1M47S",
28 "uploadDate": "2020-01-17",
29 "author": {
30 "@type": "Corporation",
31 "name": "Marketing Digital Tools"
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34 {
35 "@context": "http://schema.org",
36 "@type": "WebPage",
37 "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/planos",
38 "mainEntityOfPage": {
39 "@type": "WebPage",
40 "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/planos/",
41 "name": "Marketing Digital Tools",
42 "description": "Planos e Preços"
43 } },
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45 "@context": "http://schema.org",
46 "@type": "BlogPosting",
47 "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/Blog",
48 "image": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-content
49 "url": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/como-criar-ur
50 "headline": "Como criar um site e-commerce?",
51 "alternativeHeadline": "Marketing Digital Tools explica
52 "dateCreated": "2020-01-23",
53 "datePublished": "2020-01-23",
54 "dateModified": "2020-01-23",
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56 "isFamilyFriendly": "true",
57 "copyrightYear": "2020",
58 "copyrightHolder": "Marketing Digital Tools",
59 "contentLocation": {
60 "@type": "Place",
61 "name": "Porto, PT"
62 },
63 "accountablePerson": {
64 "@type": "Person",
65 "name": "Sérgio Julião",
66 "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
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68 "author": {
69 "@type": "Person",
70 "name": "Sérgio Julião",
71 "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
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73 "creator": {
74 "@type": "Person",
75 "name": "Sérgio Julião",
76 "url": "http://sergiojuliao.com"
77 },
78 "publisher": {
79 "@type": "Organization",
80 "@id": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/Bl
81 "name": "Marketing Digital Tools",
82 "url": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com",
83 "logo": {
84 "@type": "ImageObject",
85 "url": "http://marketingdigitaltools.com/wp-con

```

BlogPosting
 Detetado 0 ERROS (1) 2 AVISOS 7 ITENS
 Organization

BlogPosting / Organization	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	2 AVISOS	1 ITEM
BlogPosting / Organization	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
VideoObject	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
Service / WebPage	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
WebSite	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
ProfessionalService	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
FAQPage	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM
articleBody	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	0 ERROS	0 AVISOS	1 ITEM